

WATERSHED ANALYSIS- DELINEATION AND MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF BHOGAON WATERSHED BY USING REMOTE SENSING & GIS

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Abstract

The research work entitled "Watershed Analysis - Delineation, Morphological Analysis by Using Remote Sensing and GIS Technique" was carried out during the year of 2022-23 in Bhogaon watershed Parbhani district. In this research the Remote Sensing and GIS technique was used for delineation of the watershed boundary, preparing the thematic maps. The Bhogaon watershed is located in 19°35'78.78" N and 76°87'88.44" E in the Parbhani district of Marathwada region in Maharashtra. It is covered a total area 97.01 km². Digital Elevation Model (DEM) and Survey of India Toposheet no. 56A/15 was used for the watershed delineation. The low drainage density (1.45 Km/Km²) suggest that watershed is highly resistance, less slope and permeable soil Surface. Form factor (0.784) and elongation ratio (0.64) indicates that the watershed has elongated in shape. The relief ratio (0.0026) and relative relief ratio (0.07%) shows that low intensity of erosion process. Thematic maps such as Slope map, Contour map, Aspect map, Hill shade map and drainage map were prepared with the help of DEM data. but well-developed dendrites drainage pattern is there in the Bhogaon watershed.

Keywords: Remote Sensing, Geographical Information System, Morphometric analysis, Digital Elevation Model, land use/land cover.

Introduction

Soil and water are the most important and basic natural resource on the earth surface. Most of our food depends on soil and water. The soil rises slowly, taking 500 years to create 1 cm of soil (Alexander L, 2007). Flow of water is the main factors that degrade the soil. Runoff washes the soil particles from the slope of area and feels them in running water. It is important to protect the soil with the help of proper agricultural practices.

Soil and water are two of the most important and powerful natural resources that are fundamentally needed for health and for economic and social development. Agriculture plays a major role in the Indian economy with about 60 % of the people involved in agriculture and related activities and contributes 17% to the country's Gross Value

Added (Kekane, 2013). In addition, agriculture is an important source of raw material for industrial production and operates in a very large market for industrial products. According to the 2012-13 land use of the Geographical Area of India is 328.7 million hectares. The net cultivated area of 185.8 million hectares, 57.7 million hectares land is suffering from erosion due to water and wind. 40 m ha land is badly precious and needed immediate control measures. The annual soil erosion in India was assessed about 5334 million tonnes due to agricultural activities and its associates. And about 1572 million tonnes soils are sediments per year are carried away into the sea by the river of the country. Similarly, about 480 million tonne soil are deposited into various reservoir of the country.

Morphometric analysis is the precise analysis of earth's surface configuration including shape, size, landform dimensions etc. It describes the basin geometry, geomorphology, slope, rock hardness and other structural characteristics of drainage basin. Thereby, it is important for hydrological surveys of any watershed for its better management. Development and drainage system and the spatial-temporal pattern of a river flow are governed by the geology, geomorphology, soil, land use and other structural components of the area through which it flows. In at the watershed scale, geology, relief

and climates mainly determine the function of river system. The drainage morphometric characteristics also help to analyse to the watershed delineation, watershed modelling, water recharge and discharge. The geomorphologic features of the catchment area control the dynamic nature of runoff, which is very sensitive for the morphometric parameters of the watershed

Materials And Methods

This chapter has completed information about the location of study area, required materials, data and methodology used for the geographical analysis of Bhogaon watershed. In this chapter various thematic maps cover maps were prepared with the help of Survey of India Toposheet, Digital Elevation Model (DEM) and satellite images. QGIS software was used to determining the drainage pattern maps. Present study has contained a various satellite Remote Sensing data for the planning of the watershed.

Description of Study Area

Location of study area

The study area of Bhogaon watershed is located in the Godavari-Purna (GP-56) basin in Parbhani District. The watershed is lies between 19°35'78.78" N and 76°87'88.44" E in the Parbhani district of Marathwada region in Maharashtra. It is located in 16 Km towards North from the district headquarter Parbhani. The elevation/altitude is 414 meters above the sea level.

Climate and soil Condition

Climate condition is normally dry except during the south-west monsoon season of the area. The year are divided into four seasons.

Table No. 3.1 Detail of satellite data used for morphometric analysis.

Sr. No.	Type of data	Detail	Sources	Software Use
1	SOI Toposheet	Toposheet No. E43E15 (56A/15) Scale: 1:50,000	Survey of India, Nakshe Portal	QGIS (Creating and using maps, Compiling Geographic Data, Analysing Map Information and Managing Geographical Information in Database)
2	DEM (Digital Elevation Model)	Resolution- 1-ARC 30 m resolution	SRTM (SRTM 1 Arc-Second Global) From USGS (United States of Geological Survey)	
3	GPS (Global Positioning System)	To Provide a geolocation and time information to GPS receiver.	Google	Google Earth

Morphometric Analysis of Watershed by Using QGIS Software

Morphometric analysis is the very appropriate method for identifying the geographical and topological conditions of the watershed.

Delineation of Watershed

Digital Elevation Model and Toposheets used for the delineating the watershed boundary with the help of QGIS software. Steps delineating the watershed boundaries in QGIS software is given below:

Calculation of Morphometric Parameters of Watershed

The morphometric analysis is very important method for the planning and management of the watershed. Morphometrics is a technique that measuring the characteristics of the terrain, shape of the earth. It is computational measure of the geometry, topography and shape of the earths.

Table No. 3.3 Detail of Linear, Areal and Relief parameters.

Sr. No.	Morphometric Aspects	Parameters
1	Linear Aspect	i. Stream order ii. Stream Number iii. Stream Length iv. Bifurcation Ratio
2	Areal Aspect	i. Area ii. Perimeter iii. Length of watershed iv. Drainage Density v. Stream Frequency vi. Elongation Ratio vii. Circulatory Ratio viii. Form Factor ix. Length of Overland Flow x. Compactness Coefficient xi. Constant Channel Maintenance
3	Relief Aspect	i. Watershed Relief

The cold season from December to February, followed by the hot season from March to May. The southwest monsoon season is from June to September. The average annual rainfall of the Parbhani district is 882.5 mm. The temperature in summer season goes up to 42° C and 11° C in winter season. The relative humidity in the southwest monsoon season is high, ranging from 60% to 80%.

The landscape of the Parbhani district has two-contrasting feature namely the undulating agricultural land and residual plateau feature with deeply eroded side covered with the scrub and occasional stony west. Types of soil seen in area of Bhogaon watershed are, Soil in Godavari-Purna (GP-56) basins are very fertile, deep and rich in nutrients. Eastern-southern part of the Bhogaon watershed are existing in heavy black cotton soils are existing and Light and Medium soil is seen Northern-Western area of watershed.

Toposheets

The Survey of India Toposheet (SOI) No. 56A/15 on 1:50,000 scale was procured from the Survey of India from Nakshe Portal Website.

Remote Sensing and Geographical Information system based morphological analysis for the drainage and terrain analysis is very scientific and advanced tool for gathering the information about the watershed. Geographical Information System is a computer base system design to store, process and analysis of spatial data and their attributes.

The morphometric analysis of the Bhogaon watershed is carried out by calculation of Linear, Aerial and Relief parameters with the help of QGIS software and formulae suggested by the Horton, Strahler, and Miller & Schuman. Following table describes calculated Linear, Areal and Relief parameters of the watershed.

- | | | |
|--|--|---------------------------|
| | | ii. Relative Relief |
| | | iii. Relief Ratio |
| | | iv. Relative Relief ratio |
| | | v. Ruggedness Number |

Stream Length Ratio (RL)

Stream Length Ratio is the ratio of total stream length of a given order to the total stream length of its next lower order (Sreedevi, 2005). The increasing stream length ratio from lower order to higher order it indicates settled geographic stage.

Formula,

$$(RL) = L_u / L_{u-1}$$

Where,

- R_l = Stream Length Ratio
 L_u = Stream Length of Order 'U'
 L_{u-1} = Total Stream Length of Next Lower Order

Bifurcation Ratio (Rb)

Total number of stream segment of given order divided by number of stream segment of higher order is known as Bifurcation ratio (Horton, 1945). It is denoted by "Rb". The higher bifurcation ratio indicates some sort of geological control and lower bifurcation ratio indicates that drainage pattern not affect by the geological structures (Horton, 1945).

Formula

$$(R_b) = N_u / N_{u+1}$$

Where,

- R_b = Bifurcation Ratio
 N_u = Total Number of Stream Segment of Order 'U'
 N_{u+1} = Number of Stream Segment of Next Higher

Order

Areal Aspects of the Watershed**Area of Watershed (A)**

Area contain with the vertical projection of the drainage is called as Area of the watershed. It calculated by QGIS software and express in Sq. km.

Perimeter of watershed (P)

Length of watershed Boundary is called as perimeter of the watershed.

Where,

- D_t = Drainage Texture
 N = Total Number of Streams
 P = Perimeter of the Watershed

Circulatory Ratio (Rc)

Area of the watershed divided by the area of circle having same circumference as the basin perimeter is called as circulatory ratio. The circulatory ratio indicates that the shape of the basin such as watershed is circular or non-circular (Strahler, 1964).

Formula

$$R_c = 4\pi A / P^2$$

Where,

- R_c = Circulatory Ratio
 A = Area of the Watershed, Km^2
 P = Perimeter of the Watershed, Km

Form Factor (Rf)

Form factor is defined as the area of the watershed per unit square of maximum length of basin (Horton, 1945). The value of form factor must be less than 0.754.

Formula

$$R_f = A / L_b^2$$

Where,

- A = Area of the Watershed, Km^2
 L_b = Maximum Length of Watershed, Km

Elongation Ratio (Re)

Elongation ratio is defined as the diameter of the circle of the same area as the drainage basin and maximum length of basin (Horton, 1945). The elongation ratio is

= Compactness coefficient

P = Perimeter of the watershed, Km

A = Area of Watershed, Km^2

Constant Channel Maintenance (C_{cm})

Constant Channel Maintenance is the reciprocal of the drainage density (Schumn, 1956). The Constant Channel Maintenance is representing the drainage area required to maintain one unit of channel length; their fore it calculates the watershed erodibility.

Formula

$$C_{cm} = 1 / D_d$$

Where,

C_{cm} = Constant Channel Maintenance

D_d = Drainage Density, Km/Km^2

Relief Aspect of the Watershed**Basin Relief**

The relief is defined as the elevation of the highest (H) and lowest point (h) of the watershed. It calculates the slop and so the runoff and sediment transport.

Relative Relief (R)

The relative relief is defined as the difference of highest point to the lowest point of the watershed (Strahler 1964). It is also known as the total relief.

Formula

$$R = H - h$$

Where,

R = Relative Relief (Km)

$H - h$ = Difference in highest point and lowest point

Relief Ratio (R_r)

The Ratio of maximum watershed relief to the maximum watershed length is called as Relief Ratio (Schumn, 1956). The high value of relief ratio indicates steep

Result And Discussion

The present study was conducted for morphometri analysis of the Bhogaon watershed in Parbhani district of Maharashtra, using the remote sensing and geographical information system. The study was characterized into the three parts. The first part is to generating the thematic maps such as Slope map, Contour map, Aspect map, Hillshade and the Drainage map. The second part is morphometric analysis of the watershed. Morphometric aspects such as linear aspect, areal aspects and relief aspect was computed by the standard formulae recommended by the Strahler, Horton, and Millar Schumn etc. The Base map and Digital Elevation Model were also prepared by using the Survey of India Toposheet as 1: 50,000 scale. This chapter represent the result obtain by adopted methods discussed in the previous chapter and brief discussion on it.

Preparation of Various Thematic Maps

The Remote Sensing and Geographical Information System is very powerful technique to monitoring the land surface conditions with the help of a various spatial and temporal resolutions. Thematic maps show the spatial pattern of the geographical condition of the surface, climatic conditions, population density, land cover types etc. Mainly, the thematic mapping is defined as the generation of a cadastral base maps, which highlight the precise features of the terrestrial area.

The various thematic maps such as base map, slope map, contour map, hillshade map, drainage map is prepared with the help of toposheet and digital elevation model in

GIS software. The technique is very appropriate for determining the slope, contours, land covers and the drainage patterns. The analysis of these maps is shown in below:

Fig. No. 4.3 Slope Map of Bhogaon Watershed

Fig. No. 4.5 Contour Map of Bhogaon Watershed

Morphometric Parameter analysis

Linear Aspect

Table No. 4.3 Linear Parameters of the Bhogaon watershed.

Stream Orders (U)	Stream No. (Nu)	Stream Length (Lu) (Km)	Mean Stream Length (Lsm) (Km)	Stream Length Ratio (SRL)	Bifurcation Ratio (Rb)
1 st Order	97	71.64 (51.35%)	0.738	-	-
2 nd Order	54	39.96 (28.64%)	0.740	0.55	1.79
3 rd Order	19	14.625 (10.47%)	0.769	0.36	2.84
4 th Order	15	11.50 (8.24%)	0.766	0.78	1.26
5 th Order	1	1.79 (1.79%)	0.597	0.15	15
Total	186	139.5 Km	Average = 0.722	Average = 0.46	Average = 5.22

Stream Number (Nu)

Stream Number is defined as the number of streams of a different order in a drainage watershed area. Maximum Fifth order stream has found in the Bhogaon watershed. There are 97 streams of the first order, 54 streams of second order, 19 stream third order, 15 streams of fourth order and 1 stream of the fifth order. Total number of streams in the Bhogaon watershed is given in table no. 4.3.

Length (L)

Stream Length is most important linear parameter of the watershed. It was firstly introduced by the Horton in 1945. Horton defines the stream length as the total length of all order stream in a specific order. Generally, in stream length if stream order is increases then the total length of stream segments will decrease. Length of first order stream is always more than the next higher order stream.

Stream length in the Bhogaon watershed was measure with the help of the QGIS software. Total stream length of the watershed is 139.5 Km. after the analysis of the stream length of all order it reveals that nearly 51.35% stream length of first order. The percentage of second order, third order, fourth order and fifth orders stream lengths are 28.64 %,

10.47 %, 8.24 % and 1.28 % respectively the deviation in the stream length gives the indication that terrain surface has a moderately steep slope and moderate relief. Total length of all order streams is 139.5 Km is given in table no. 4.3.

Mean Stream Length (Lsm)

Mean Stream length is the linear parameter of the morphometric analysis, it was firstly introduced by the Strahler in 1964. It is a dimensional property revealing the characteristic size of component of a drainage network and its watershed surface. Mean stream length is calculated by dividing the total stream length of a given order to the total number of stream segment of given order. It is express in Kilometres. Average length of first order, second order, third order, fourth order and fifth order streams are 0.738, 0.740, 0.769, 0.766 and 0.597 km. the average length of each stream is given in table no. 4.3.

The areal aspects are consisting of the Area, Perimeter, Length of watershed, drainage density, drainage texture, stream frequency, elongation ratio, circulatory ratio, Length of overland flow, form factor, constant channel maintenance etc. for the morphological analysis of the watershed.

Table 4.4 Areal Parameters of the Bhogaon watershed

Sr. No.	Areal parameters	Units	Value
1	Area (A)	Km ²	97.01
2	Perimeter (P)	Km	70
3	Length of watershed (L _b)	Km	17.63
4	Drainage Density (D _d)	Km/Km ²	1.45
5	Drainage Texture (D _t)	Km ⁻¹	2.7
6	Stream Frequency (F _s)	Km ⁻²	1.93
7	Elongation Ratio (Re)	-	0.630
8	Circulatory Ratio (R _c)	-	0.25
9	Length of overland flow (L _o)	Km	0.34
10	Form Factor (R _f)	-	0.31
11	Constant Channel Maintenance (C _{cm})	-	0.68
12	Compactness Coefficient (C _c)	-	2.00

Morphometric Analysis of Bhogaon watershed

Linear Aspect

The linear aspects of the watershed are related to the channel pattern of the drainage networks where the topological characteristics of the stream segments in terms of open links of the network streams are analysed. Stream numbers, length, Bifurcation ratio, stream length ratio are the parameters of the linear aspects.

Stream Order (U)

Stream order is the first step of the morphometric analysis of the watershed. The stream ordering system is firstly introduced by the Horton (1945) in United States of America. It defines the position of a stream in the order of the tributaries. After that Horton the Strahler has modified the drainage network system. According to the Strahler, when two first order stream joins it form a second order stream, two second order stream join each other it gets third order stream. The process will continue till to obtain the higher order stream. Higher order stream is called as the 'Trunk' stream. Maximum order stream brings the sediment and runoff at the outlet of the watershed.

According to the Strahler's method of the stream ordering the highest Fifth Order stream has been found in the Bhogaon watershed. It was also observed that when the stream order is increases the number of tributaries decreases. Figure 4.3 shows that drainage map and stream order of the Bhogaon watershed from the first order to fifth order.

Stream Length Ratio (S_n)

Stream Length Ratio is the ratio of total stream length of a order to the total stream length of its next lower order. Stream length ratio indicates

Table No. 4.5 Relief Parameters of the Bhogaon Watershed

Sr. No.	Relief Parameters	Units		Values	
1	Maximum Elevation (R)	Meter	Km	419	0.419
2	Minimum Elevation (r)	Meter	Km	370	0.370
3	Relative Relief (H)	Meter	Km	49	0.049
4	Relief Ratio (R _r)	-		0.0026	
5	Relative Relief Ratio (H _r)	%		0.07	
6	Ruggedness Number (R _n)	-		0.074	

Relief Aspects

Relief parameter specifies that the vertical dimensions of the catchment area and indicating the three-dimensional features such as the area, volume, altitude and elevation of the terrain surface. Relief aspect has function of measurement of elevation at the specific point of the catchment area. Relief aspect contains the watershed relief, relative relief, relief ratio and the ruggedness number

Relative relief of the Bhogaon watershed is 49 M which is obtain by taking the difference between highest and lowest elevation of the watershed. There by the Bhogaon watershed has a low relative relief.

Relief Ratio

The term of the relief ratio is firstly express by the Schumm in 1963 and defines that as total relief to the length of the watershed. It describes that the relief ratio measures that the overall steepness of the watershed. If the drainage area is increases then the relief ratio is increases. Relief ratio is a good indicator of intensity of the erosion

that the changes in the watershed, which describe the variation in slope and topography; variation in the stream length ratio reveals that the late youth stage of geo-morphological cycle.

Stream length ratio of Bhogaon watershed is varying from 0.55 to 0.15 and the average stream length ratio of the watershed is 0.46. All the values of stream length ratio are given in table no. 4.3.

Bifurcation Ratio (R_b)

Total number of stream segment of given order divided by number of stream segment of higher order is known as Bifurcation ratio. It is denoted by "R_b". Bifurcation ratio classifies into two classes namely as lower class (R_b less than 5) and higher class (R_b greater than 5). The higher bifurcation ratio indicates structural control on the development of drainage pattern and lower bifurcation ratio indicates that geomorphological control. Bifurcation ratio is depending on the geology and lithology of the watershed.

After analysing the bifurcation ratio of a various order streams; the Mean Bifurcation Ratio of the Bhogaon watershed has 5.21 which is more than the 5. The higher bifurcation ratio indicates structural control on the development of drainage pattern and lower bifurcation ratio indicates that geomorphological control. Bifurcation ratio of the all-orders streams are shown in table no. 4.3.

Length of watershed

Length of watershed is longest flow path means the line from the mouth of the stream to the furthest pint of the watershed. The longest flow path of the watershed is measure with the help of ArcGIS 10.8 software. The length of the watershed is 17.63 Km.

process on the slope of the watershed also it is closely correlated to the peak discharge and runoff intensity.

Relief ratio of the Bhogaon watershed is 0.0026 which indicates that study area has a low relief ratio. It is a dimensionless term. The low relief ratio indicates that the Bhogaon watershed has low degree of slope.

Relative Relief Ratio

Melton (1957) has been discovered the term of relative relief ratio. It defines as the ratio of the total relief (difference between the highest and lowest elevation of the watershed) to the perimeter of the watershed. This term is generally express in percentage (%). Relative relief ratio of the Bhogaon watershed is 0.07%.

Ruggedness Number

The ruggedness number is defined as the product of total relief (H) (difference between the highest and lowest point of the study area) and drainage density (D_d) of the watershed (Petton & Baker 1976). The

ruggedness number shows that the structural intricacy of the terrain surface in association with relief as well as drainage density and it also indicates that the soil surface is susceptible to the erosion. It is a dimensionless term.

In case of the Bhogaon watershed the value of the ruggedness number is 0.0714 which indicates that the study area low ruggedness number and low ruggedness number suggest that the watershed area less prone to the soil erosion and have intrinsic structural relation with relief and drainage density.

Conclusions

Land and water are the two most valuable natural resources, and their significance in human civilization is self-evident. Because land and water availability are considered to be one of the most essential factors for rapid development and urbanisation, planning and managing natural resources in a sustainable manner has become a major concern, particularly in areas where land and water are scarce. As a result, the mainstay of mankind is the planning and management of land and water resources on a long-term basis without deterioration and with a steady growth in production. The watershed or is an appropriate unit for its efficient and long-term management.

Keeping in view above the facts the current research was carried out with the goal of determining the morphometric characteristics of a watershed in an RS and GIS technique,

1. The area of the Bhogaon watershed is 97.01 km². Most of the Bhogaon watershed is consist of the gentle slope 2-5 % and nearly level 0-2 %. According to the gentle slope area characteristics this is more suitable for constructing water conservation structures and cultivation and the nearly level surface is useful for storing the water for irrigation purpose.
2. The total stream length is 139.5 km, which is the direct outcome of drainage development in a particular watershed. The basin contains total 188 number of streams.
3. Drainage density is a measure of the texture of drainage system within a unit area. Bhogaon watershed has drainage density of 1.45 Km/Km² indicating coarse drainage texture due to highly resistant sub-soil material.
4. The stream frequency is 1.93 streams/km² exhibits the positive correlation with the drainage density. The form factor, elongation ratio and circulatory ratio indicate that the whole watershed has elongated in shape. This indicates that sub-soil has higher infiltration rate, time of concentration is more and lower peak flow for longer duration.
5. Bhogaon watershed has highest relief is 419 meter and lowest relief 370 meter. The elevation difference of highest and lowest relief is 49 meters.

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